

Newsletter 1 / 2020

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Save the date ESIWACE2 annual meeting and ENES HPC Workshop

The ESIWACE annual meeting 2020 will take place on Wednesday, May 27 at DKRZ in Hamburg. It will be preceded by the ENES HPC meeting on Monday and Tuesday May 25+26.

Details at

<https://www.esiwace.eu/events>

Invitation to the Summer School on Effective HPC for Climate and Weather

Making effective use of computing systems is challenging for users and scientific software engineers. In particular, PhD students and young researchers often struggle with the technical nature of the tools and environment that sustains their computer-aided research.

The scope of the summer school is the training of young researchers and software engineers in methods, tools, and theoretical knowledge to make effective use of HPC environments and help them to generate scientific insights. The school is supported by experts from international institutions that will be providing lectures and hands-on training on their field of expertise.

- Date: 23-28 August 2020
- Venue: University of Reading, Whiteknights Campus, Reading, UK, RG6 6UR
- Contact: Julian Kunkel <j.m.kunkel@reading.ac.uk>

The Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe (ESIWACE2) provides grants for travel and attendance.

Further information: <https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2020/esiwace-school>

Events that ESIWACE will participate or has participated in

- [Machine Learning for Weather and Climate Modelling Workshop](#), Oxford, UK, 2-5 September 2019
- [1st Artificial Intelligence for Copernicus Workshop](#), ECMWF, Reading, UK 5-7 November 2019
- [Supercomputing 2019](#), Denver, Colorado, USA, 17-22 November 2019
- [Container Hackathon for Modellers](#), Lugano, CH, 3-5 December 2019
- [Hamburg COMMODORE conference](#), Hamburg, DE, 28-31 January, 2020
- [DRAKKAR 2020 Annual Workshop](#), Grenoble, FR, 3-5 February 2020
- [Special Interest Group IO in the UK](#), Reading, UK 23rd April, 2020

News & updates

Containerization Hackathon

Lucas Benedicic reporting for WP2

In early December 2019, ETH Zurich hosted a *Container Hackathon for Modellers* at CSCS in Lugano, Switzerland. The objective of the event was to give participants the opportunity of creating Docker-container versions of different weather- and climate simulation codes. Containers have gained a lot of attention in recent years due to their ability to provide a consistent environment to ensure security, portability and performance. Since the container is built only once, but then can be deployed on multiple platforms, productivity is increased. The organizers assigned a dedicated, experienced mentor to each of the teams working on a particular code. Additionally, the teams were given the

possibility of launching their containers at scale on the Piz Daint supercomputing system. Fifteen researchers representing seven different modelling codes participated and successfully created containers with their codes, the code of which can be found at <https://github.com/eth-cscs/ContainerHackathon>
A report summarizing the created material and experience is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3685888>

Four projects awarded funding in the ESIWACE2 Service 1 call

Ben van Werkhoven reporting for WP3

The Netherlands eScience Center and Atos Bull grant support to four proposals within the ESIWACE2 project. The granted projects will receive consultancy, advice, and engineering from the research software engineers at the eScience center and Atos. These collaborative projects will allow experts in high-performance computing (HPC) and accelerated computing to work together with the model developers to advance the software so that (parts of) the model can be executed efficiently on modern CPU processors or modern computing accelerators, such as Graphics Processing Units (GPUs). Read more about the projects starting in 2020 on the ESIWACE website:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpc-userservices/four-projects-awarded-funding-in-the-esiwace2-service-1-call>

ESDM PAV Architecture description published

Sandro Fiore reporting for ESIWACE2 WP5

A milestone on the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) Architecture design (M5.1) has been published. The report provides insights into the design of the ESDM interface for supporting data-intensive *post-processing*, *analytics* and *visualization* (PAV) applications in the weather and climate domains. The proposed architecture addresses the identified requirements and provides the guidelines to steer the development over the next years of the project. Find the full document at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3592384>

ESiWACE 1 Final review

Florian Ziemen reporting for the ESIWACE 1 WPL

ESiWACE 1 passed its final review in Luxemburg in December with flying colors. The reviewers and the EC were very happy with the work we have done. The only criticism was that we have to present our work a bit better to the public. We will take this as encouragement and guideline for the work in ESIWACE2.

CoE Cluster Review

Florian Ziemen and Joachim Biercamp

Two weeks after the ESIWACE final review, we were in Luxemburg again for a review of all Centres of Excellence. Again, ESIWACE was mentioned as a positive example regarding the clear scientific concept and the societal relevance of the work. In this meeting we discussed the Centres' perspectives on the challenges regarding making full use of (pre-) exascale computers, ways to better involve the smaller EU countries, and to improve the gender balance in the project teams and in workshops and trainings offered. The experts of the EC will provide a summary of the results. We agreed to feature the other CoEs ([CHEESE](#), [EoCoE](#), [POP](#)) at our EGU Booth in May.

ESiWACE extreme scale IFS demonstrator in “production”

ECMWF has been awarded time on Summit - the world’s most powerful supercomputer - as part of the US INCITE programme for 2020. The allocation will allow the ECMWF to run the global IFS model at 1.45 km resolution for a full season, and potentially an entire year, and to handle the vast amounts of data this will produce. More information can be found at

<https://www.ecmwf.int/en/about/media-centre/news/2020/ecmwf-scientists-simulate-global-weather-1-km-resolution>

Selfie of the PI of the project -- Nils Wedi -- in front of the Summit cooling system and the front rack (left), and a picture down one of the many aisles (right).

Snapshots

BSC

BSC is continuing the developments of the mixed precision version of the NEMO code. There is a working version running on Mare Nostrum 4 and a scalability analysis is being performed. On the other hand, BSC has been working on a set of benchmarks to evaluate the performance of the OpenIFS-XIOS model.

Bull Atos & NLeSC

Together with ATOS, the Netherlands eScience Center will be starting four new projects as part of the ESiWACE2 Service 1 call for projects. In these projects, we will provide guidance, advice, and engineering to help to prepare Europe’s weather and climate models for future pre-exascale systems. You can read more about the projects starting in 2020 on the ESiWACE website:

<https://www.esiwace.eu/services/hpc-userservices/four-projects-awarded-funding-in-the-esiwace2-service-1-call>

CERFACS

Work has started and is well advanced on the production of the OASIS3-MCT online training course material. Also the selection for 2020 dedicated service on OASIS3-MCT (WP3, service 2) took place in December: NERSC Bergen was granted 2 months of dedicated support for coupling ocean and dynamic ice sheet models.

CMCC

Activities on the global ORCA36 ocean-sea ice configuration are proceeding. The sea ice model SI3 has been better adapted to the resolution of the system. The code, now available and running on two different machines, is numerically stable. Optimizations of the I/O package and subsetting of output variables was needed. The Milestone 5.1 led by CMCC on the “ESDM Architecture” has been achieved at the end of December 2019. In this respect, a technical report has also been delivered and published on Zenodo. After the release of the preliminary architecture in December, CMCC is working with the other partners on the definition of the APIs for the ESDM processing, analytics and visualization extensions.

DKRZ

The project office has finished the final report of ESIWACE with the help of all teams. The new team is finding its way through the project. We have represented ESIWACE at the two review meetings in Luxemburg in December. DKRZ has contributed to the WP5 document on the ESDM PAV infrastructure led by CMCC and is contributing to the set up of the new DYAMOND configuration.

ECMWF

Work on a single precision version of NEMO that could potentially be used within numerical weather predictions at ECMWF continued. We also ran first simulations that used a 4 km IFS atmosphere model coupled to a ¼ degree NEMO model and the WAM wave model.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

ETH Zurich / CSCS prepared for and carried out the “Container Hackathon” Dec. 3-5, 2020. Seven teams (15 total participants) from the ESIWACE-2 community encapsulated their models into Docker containers. The results of the hackathon went well beyond expectations: every team managed to containerise their application, and deploy it at least on one target platform. Some teams successfully ran their containers at scale on the CSCS Piz Daint platform using the locally-developed SARUS container framework. The workshop reviews were resoundingly positive. The materials and reports from the hackathon were published in deliverable D2.8 (doi:[10.5281/zenodo.3685888](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3685888)).

ICHEC

ICHEC will be providing testing facilities for WP4. ICHEC has automated build systems and continuous testing with automated compilation and deployment, Jenkins servers, and VMs as well as containers on the HPC system Kay. ICHEC has been using Singularity / Docker containers, running the ESGF Docker implementation, deploying the data (CMIP and CORDEX) via Jenkins for multiple projects.

MPI-M

Work on the cdo optimisation described earlier continued. A first test installation of ECMWFs FDB5 system has successfully been installed.

Mercator Ocean (MO)

A first version of the new global 1/36° configuration has been developed with NEMO v4 OGCM. A 3 months simulation has been produced on the ECMWF CRAY CCA supercomputer, using around 12.000 cores. 7-days 3D outputs and hourly 2D outputs were produced thanks to the XIOS library.

Met Office

We have been having preliminary discussions with University of Reading to establish requirements for cylc changes to support the vision of enabling workflows to have an understanding of data and I/O requirements.

SMHI

Work is ongoing to develop the production-mode configuration for EC-Earth4. Tests have been started with a pre-release of OpenIFS 43r3, which is coupled to NEMO4.0.1 at this stage. The build and runtime environment is undergoing major development, which is, among other things, needed to handle new OpenIFS grid choices in a more flexible fashion. Part of the development on OpenIFS is provided to the ECMWF OpenIFS team for upstream integration.

STFC (UKRI)

PSyclone development is continuing in support of the translation of the NEMO tracer-advection benchmark to the Stencil Intermediate Representation (SIR), which can then be run through the Dawn optimising back-end, which is being developed by MeteoSwiss. In particular, the SIR does not support the Fortran intrinsics found in the benchmark (ABS, MIN and SIGN). Therefore PSyclone transformations have been developed (and are currently in review) which translate these intrinsics to their inlined equivalent (in PSyclone's internal representation [PSyIR]). The NEMO tracer-advection benchmark is very similar to the proposed ESCAPE2 NEMO dwarf, so this work will move to the dwarf when it is released.

PSyclone-generated NEMO GPU code (for the ORCA1-SI3-GO8 configuration) running on an NVIDIA V100, has been updated to use the latest PGI compiler (19.10). This required the addition of OpenACC loop directives to those loops that the new version of the compiler refused to parallelise using the OpenACC Kernels directive. With these changes the original performance (with 19.7) has now been recovered.

Work continues to improve support for Fortran array slice notation. This will help both the full NEMO configuration and the tracer-advection benchmark.

University of Reading

The compatibility report for the NetCDF integration of ESDM is released and it can be accessed in the ESDM NetCDF repository <https://github.com/ESiWACE/esdm-netcdf/>. Together with this report, there is information about the current status for the ESDM deployment through Jenkins Continuous Integration (CI). For ESDM, active storage

computing designs are being improved considering hardware capabilities of DDN's IME and Seagate's Clovis and, together with DKRZ, we started the preparation of a paper investigating optimal data mappings for write/read phases.

In parallel, the summer school webpage (<https://hps.vi4io.org/events/2020/esiwace-school>) went live on January 20 and we are disseminating information about it to raise awareness and encourage registrations.

Ongoing activities are:

- 1) together with DKRZ, we are currently investigating the impact of data mappings during read/write phases on the performance of ESDM.
- 2) A vision paper is being prepared to establish the partnership among MetOffice, DDN and the University of Reading. This work presents an innovative integration of I/O into workflows managed by Cylc and using vendor-specific migration capabilities.
- 3) We will organize at the Supercomputing Frontiers - 2020 conference a session about data-centric I/O. Additionally, Birds-of-a-Feather sessions are being prepared for ISC, with the following central topics: Data-Centric I/O, HPC Certification, and IO500.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

Betke, E. and Kunkel, J.: Footprinting Parallel I/O – Machine Learning to Classify Application's I/O Behavior, in Lecture Notes in Computer Science, pp. 214–226, Springer International Publishing., 2019.

Hatfield, S., McRae, A., Palmer, T. and Düben, P.: Single-precision in the tangent-linear and adjoint models of incremental 4D-Var, Monthly Weather Review, doi:[10.1175/mwr-d-19-0291.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/mwr-d-19-0291.1), 2020.

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